

1 *Supplementary materials*

2 **Rice husk biochars modified with magnetized iron**
3 **oxides and nano zero valent iron for decolorization of**
4 **dyeing wastewater treatment**

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17 **Materials and methods**

18 *Full-scale gasifier used for producing gasification biochar:* Figure S1 presents a full-scale gasifier (BiGchar
19 2200 fast rotary hearth, $\phi = 2.2$ m, $h = 2$ m, nominal capacity of 300 kg biochar / h, designed and
20 fabricated in Australia by Black is Green) which was used to produce the full-scale gasification biochar.
21 The gasifier has four chambers equipped temperature and air controllers.
22

Figure S1: Full-scale gasification system (BiGchar 2200 fast rotary hearth, Australia) for biochar production. Owned by Ecofarm Co. Ltd, Long An province, Vietnam.

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24 *Lab-scale closed furnace used for producing pyrolysis biochar:* Figure S2 presents a lab-scale closed furnace (Lenton EF 11/8B, UK) and other associated equipments (the steel cylinder) which were used for
25 producing pyrolysis biochar (Figure S2).
26
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Figure S2: (a) Lab-scale furnace (Lenton EF 11/8B, UK) for biochar production; (b) closed-steel cylinder for containing biomass; (c) components of the closed-steel cylinder.

28

29 The yield of biochar was calculated as following:

30
$$\text{Biochar yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{mass of biochar (g)}}{\text{dried mass of biomass (g)}} \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. S1})$$

31 Ash content of biochars was determined by a dry combustion method [1]. In brief, about 5.0 g
32 of biochar was heated at 500 °C for 8 h. The crucible was then cooled to room temperature and
33 reweighed. The ash content was calculated as following:

34
$$\text{Ash content (\%)} = \frac{\text{weight of ash (g)}}{\text{dried mass of biochar (g)}} \times 100 \quad (\text{Eq. S2})$$

35 The pH of the original biochars was determined according to Savova, Apak [2]. About 4.0 g biochar
36 was mixed with 100 mL water in a conical flask. The flask was boiled for 5 minutes and left for cooling to
37 room temperature. The supernatant was decanted and determined pH value using a pH meter (ProDSS,
38 Xylem, USA).

39 The pH of zero point of charge (pH_{ZPC}) of the biochars was determined following the previous
40 published work [3]. To a series of Erlenmeyer flasks (100 mL), 40 mL of NaNO₃ (0.1 M) solution was
41 added and the pH was adjusted by using HNO₃ and NaOH with variable concentrations (0.1 – 1 M) in
42 the pH range of 2–10. To each flask, 0.1 g biochar was added and the suspensions were agitated at a
43 stirring speed of 250 rpm overnight at room temperature. The next day, final pH (pH_f) of the suspensions
44 was recorded and the difference between final and initial pH (ΔpH) was plotted against initial pH (pH_i).
45 The pH value where net surface charge was zero, is considered to be the pH_{ZPC} of the materials.

46
47 *Assessing the loss of color due to the use of centrifuge tube (PE, 50 mL) and syringe filter (PES, 0.45 μm):* for
48 the centrifuge tube, a volume (25 mL) of every RR195, RY145, and RB19 stock was transferred to the sterile
49 tubes and shaken for 0 (control treatment) and 1 h at 150 rpm (orbital shaker, Yamato SA300). The tubes
50 were then centrifuged for 30 mins at 4000 rpm (Rotofix 32A) and finally determined color concentration
51 (in Pt-Co) by an UV-VIS spectrometer analyzer (Shimadzu UV1800). For the syrinse filters, color
52 concentrations of the RR195, RY145, and RB19 stocks were determined before and after filtration.

54 *Color loss due to the use of syrinse filter and centrifuge tube*

55 For the syringe filter, color concentrations of the RR195, RY145, and RB19 stocks decreased
56 from 408.8 ± 0.0 to 402.9 ± 1.39 Pt-Co; 404.5 ± 0.0 to 398.8 ± 1.2 Pt-Co, and 410.9 ± 0.0 to 404.9 ± 1.15 Pt-
57 Co, equivalent to the losses of 1.42 ± 0.34 %; 1.40 ± 0.30 %, and 1.46 ± 0.28 % (n = 3), respectively. With
58 the centrifuge tube after periods of 1 h contacting time, color of the RR195, RY145, and RB19 stocks
59 decreased from 408.8 ± 0 to 403.8 ± 1.2 Pt-Co; from 404.5 ± 0 to 389.0 ± 6.90 Pt-Co; and from 410.9 ± 0 to
60 405.8 ± 2.0 Pt-Co, equivalent to the losses of 1.22 ± 0.28 %; 3.8 ± 1.7 %, and 1.2 ± 0.5 % (n = 3), respectively.
61 These results presented that the color loss of the RR195, RY145, and RB19 stocks due to the use of
62 syringe filter and centrifuge tube were not significant (< 5%).

64 **References**

- 65 1. Song, W. and M. Guo, Quality variations of poultry litter biochar generated at different pyrolysis
66 temperatures. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis*, **2012**. 94: p. 138-145.
67 2. Savova, D., E. Apak, et al., Biomass conversion to carbon adsorbents and gas. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, **2001**.
68 21(2): p. 133-142.
69 3. Shah, I., R. Adnan, et al., Iron Impregnated Activated Carbon as an Efficient Adsorbent for the Removal
70 of Methylene Blue: Regeneration and Kinetics Studies. *PLOS ONE*, **2015**. 10(4): p. e0122603.

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